

Cultivating ORCID - growing a sustainable national consortium.

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Overview.

Jisc runs the ORCID consortium in the UK. Since the start of the consortium in 2015 it was our mission to improve ORCID uptake, improve the technical infrastructure and make the consortium a sustainable concern. We currently have 86 members who have just renewed their membership for 3 years and reaching this point has been a journey which has required getting national agreement with funders/stakeholders, running pilot projects through to setting up service infrastructure and developing a business model for sustainability. To provide an attractive service which is sustainable we have had to spin a number of plates and continue to look at ways in which we can provide value for the consortium such as developing software to influencing change with third party vendors.

Background.

As mentioned above Jisc realised that in order to implement ORCID in the UK we needed to get national agreement. We coordinated a joint statement in support of ORCID (ARMA, HEFCE, HESA, RCUK, UCISA, Wellcome Trust, Jisc); and a joint implementation plan which included running the [Jisc ARMA ORCID Pilot](#) projects (May 2014 – March 2015). These were 8 University based pilots to look at how to streamline ORCID implementation processes at universities and start to develop a community of practice.

We also produced a [cost-benefits analysis](#) report to help us develop the best value approach for a potential UK wide adoption of ORCID in Higher Education (HE), including evaluating the possibility of UK consortium membership.

Setting the foundations

In order to support and scaffold the initial growth of the consortium, Jisc decided to subsidise the consortium for the first 3 years. As part of the cost benefits analysis, we had surveyed UK institutions to ask if Jisc were to offer ORCID through a consortium at a competitive price, would they do so. 50 institutions responded to say that they would join the consortium; which gave Jisc the green light to go ahead with developing the consortium. The first 3 years focused on:

- Developing tailored resources such as systems capability documents
- Setting up helpdesk infrastructure
- Developing service level agreements
- Understanding the current technical landscape, gathering and synthesising requirements for exploration and development.
- Building capacity for supporting the consortium (a service team with the appropriate skills)
- Developing a culture and community within the consortium that can share practice and experience
- Developing a business plan for sustainability beyond the initial 3 years.

Developing the culture and community

We realised (as mentioned above) that an important element for sustainability was to develop a community of practice and keep the community engaged in conversation. We had the advantage that some institutions were already engaged through the Jisc ARMA pilot projects. We took several approaches in order to grow this community. As part of the service we have (and continue to):

- Run hackdays to scope define and develop new applications/solutions where appropriate
- Deliver webinars to update members on new requirements and services such as ORCID Self Service and eprints ORCID plug-in demo
- Provide training e.g. using the ORCID API
- Organise expert meetings such as for those with an interest in how to mediate interactions with [third party services](#)
- Facilitate interactions between members with common interests e.g. [those using similar institutional systems](#)
- Organise community interactions via a mailing list and annual ORCID members meeting ([Members meeting report](#))

Views from the helicopter . . . infrastructure and identity

Whilst it is important to grow the community aspect of the consortium, it has also been important to keep abreast of developments in the wider aspects of the landscape, on behalf of our community, that feed into the activities, initiatives and policies that concern the membership. Just on numbers alone, the growth of ORCID iD registered to a UK institution has been phenomenal [Figure 1.] As also noted in the [THOR report](#): *In Europe especially, multiple peaks in the overall upward trend suggest that specific initiatives have had an impact on uptake. This is most clearly apparent in the quarters ending September and December 2015 (when the JISC ORCID consortium and auto-update feature launched) when the number of ORCID works peaked here, but not in other regions* Concomitantly, during the initial 3 years of the consortium, the amount of publishers and funders that require an ORCID iD for at least one researcher has greatly increased.

Figure 1. Growth in ORCID iD associated with a .ac.uk email address

More subtly, there have been changes and evolutions to infrastructure and policies that impact on how personal information and identifiers are utilised and shared. As any European will be aware, a major component of this change has been the introduction of the GDPR legislation which has had both obvious and subtle impacts on policy, functionality and activities of all systems that involves personal information, of which ORCID iD is a case in point.

During this initial time, there has also been an expansion within the UK HE sector of the adoption of CRIS systems and rationalisation of repositories as REF2020 approaches which has led to a requirement for the centralisation of information about researchers around these systems. The consortium has been working with its members in ensuring that the infrastructure has been kept up to date to allow the best integration with ORCID iD to allow these important Researcher-centric identifiers to flow freely in institutional infrastructure. For example, from 2016 to 2018, Jisc supported the development of the eprints ORCID Advance plugin from framing the requirements to testing - this was built by eprints services ([eprints Bazaar](#) & [Code on GitHub](#)). Also we have been able to influence Symplectic to review and revise their product development roadmap for their ORCID integration features after we gathered requirements from the UK user base.

Wider PID initiatives and involvement

One area of interest to the Jisc UK ORCID consortium community is to agree standard ways, or at least conventions, on exposing ORCID IDs, recorded in institutional repositories, to downstream services. The theme of a session held during DCMI in September 2018 was therefore very relevant as the topic was Persistent Identifiers in Dublin Core. Working with our consortium community, Jisc submitted a [user story](#) that captured requirements for adding ORCID IDs to Dublin Core metadata – this was based on information gathered through hack days and other UK consortium activities. The session at DCMI came up with a [proposal](#) to be discussed more widely.

As a community, the UK Consortium is involved in the ORCID in Repositories consultation through a dedicated [task force](#) where the impacts of various repository technologies and policies are examined and explored then outcomes summarised and communicated back to our members.

Spinning plates

In building the new model we have taken into account the need to make the consortium sustainable without central Jisc funding, but still making it financially attractive to join the Jisc consortium which includes the technical support and community engagement. Our aim is to provide clear value add and discounted access to infrastructure.

Within the renewal cycle we have learned important lessons about dealing with institutional processes and procedures that needed to be factored in and worth sharing:

- Start sustainability business modelling at least 1.5 years ahead of when you need to implement any new pricing model.
- Allow enough time for the consultation process with stakeholders/community
- Give institutions enough time to factor in reviewing new licence with legal teams, getting sign-off from budget holders and to align with internal spending cycles

- Remain active and engaged with the membership to be aware of staff turnover

As we look back on these initial 3 years of the consortium pilot and move into a new phase with a new model, we can see that sustainability requires focus on numerous activities from developing infrastructure, monitoring integration, engaging the community, business modelling, communications planning to gathering and synthesising requirements, and not letting any of these plates fall.

In Conclusion: Providing value-add

As we go forward we will continue to do all of the above and already we are moving into a new phase of supporting the development of requirements and specifications for tool-chains to enhance access to members' ORCID-related information currently dispersed across disparate systems, facilitating the adoption of adaptations to profiles and metadata where they become available and generally ensuring that the information flows smoothly, effectively and efficiently across members' infrastructure. To keep members engaged and on board we need to keep providing value-add to our members and this is imbedded into the sustainability ethos.